

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH | xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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«Og‘ir ekologik sharoitga qaramasdan, mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shib kelayotgan Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini, uning barcha shahar, tuman va ovullarini kompleks tarzda rivojlantirish, mehnatkash va matonatli, oqko‘ngil va bag‘rikeng qoraqalpoq elining hayotini obod va farovon etishga har qachongidan ham ustuvor ahamiyat qaratamiz.

Bizning oliy va ezgu maqsadimiz – birgalikdagi fidokorona mehnatimiz bilan Yangi O‘zbekiston tarkibida Yangi Qoraqalpog‘istonni bunyod etishdir.»

Sh.M.MIRZIYOYEV
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Prezident: “Bu ko‘prik o‘zbek va qoraqalpoq xalqlari o‘rtasidagi og‘zibirlik va hamkorlik ko‘prigidir”.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini Xorazm viloyati bilan bog‘lovchi ko‘prik. Asosiy qo‘shma ko‘prikning uzunligi 413 metr bo‘lib, eni 8 metr; har bir oraliq‘i 66 metrni tashkil qiladi. Uning 7 ta ustuni 6 ta oraliqqa o‘rnatilgan.

KIRISH

2024-yilning 17–18-may kunlari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi Xo‘jayli tumanida o‘tkazilgan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy madaniy, etnografik va ekologik merosini keng jamoatchilikka tanitishda hamda turizm infratuzilmalarini mustahkamlashda muhim qadam bo‘ldi

Anjumanning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozoriga olib kirish va madaniy xabardorlikni oshirishdir. Qoraqalpog‘iston o‘zining tarixiy boyliklari, arxeologik yodgorliklari va o‘ziga xos tabiiy manzaralari bilan dunyo sayyohlarini jalb etadigan katta jozibadorlikka ega. Bu hududda jahon madaniy va tabiiy merosi obyektlariga mansub ko‘plab joylar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning aksariyati turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishga asos bo‘ladi.

Xususan, Qoraqalpog‘istondagi insoniyat tamaddunidan hikoya qiluvchi arxeologik yodgorliklar bisyor. Hozirgi kunda Qoraqalpog‘istonda 300 dan ortiq arxeologik obyektlar mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan eng mashhurlari – Ko‘hna Urganch, Tupraqal‘a, Ellikqal‘a va Ayoqal‘a hududlaridagi qadimiy manzillardir. Bular, o‘z navbatida, sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirib, hududning turistik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha muhokamalar o‘tkazildi. Birinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalariga bag‘ishlanib, mahalliy infratuzilmalarni takomillashtirish hamda turizm xizmatlarini kengaytirish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi. Ikkinchi yo‘nalishda etnografik turizmni rivojlantirish, xususan, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni targ‘ib etish va milliy madaniy boyliklarni namoyish qilish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Uchinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari orqali targ‘ib qilish masalalariga bag‘ishlandi.

Ushbu anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish yo‘lida muhim qadamdir. Turizm, madaniy meros va ekologik yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan taklif va tavsiyalar hududni xalqaro turistik xaritada o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lishiga yordam beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi tarixiy, madaniy va tabiiy boyliklarga ega hudud sifatida nafaqat O‘zbekiston, balki butun Markaziy Osiyoda alohida o‘rin tutadi. Bu hududni «ochiq osmon ostidagi arxeologik muzey» deb atash mumkin, chunki bu yerda qadimiy Xorazm madaniyatining markazi bo‘lgan Qoraqalpog‘istonda nafaqat arxeologik meros, balki etnografik va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Qoraqalpog‘istonda o‘tkaziladigan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro anjuman ana

shunday salohiyatni namoyon etish va rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan. Anjuman doirasida turli olimlar, tadqiqotchilar va xalqaro ekspertlar ishtirokida ekologik barqarorlik va madaniy merosni saqlash masalalari muhokama qilinib, zamonaviy turizm yo‘nalishlaridagi ilmiy-nazariy takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha quyidagi muhokamalar o‘tkazildi:

- *Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari;*
- *Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning asosiy xususiyatlari;*
- *Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida targ‘ib qilishning zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari.*

Anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida ekologik va etnografik turizm nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga tanitishga yordam berishi olgari surildi.

Anjumanda xalqaro institutlar vakillarining qatnashishi bejiz emas. Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy tarixi va Xorazm madaniyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan qadimiy yodgorliklar va arxeologik topinmalar bu hududni nafaqat tarixchilar, arxeologlar uchun, balki turistlar uchun ham jozibadorligini oshirib boradi.

Masalan, Ko‘kcha III qabristoni – qadimgi bronza davri madaniyatiga oid yodgorlik bo‘lib, millioddan avvalgi XIII-XI asrlarga oid, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu madaniyatlar ko‘p asrlar davomida bir-biri bilan hamkorlikda yashaganini va turli etnik guruhlarning madaniy merosini o‘zida mujassam etganini ko‘rsatadi.

Masalan, S.P. Tolstov¹ tomonidan o‘rganilgan Tazabagyab madaniyatlari ham Qoraqalpog‘istonning arxeologik salohiyatining muhim qismi bo‘lib, ularni o‘rganish natijasida bronza davrining ikki madaniyati bir vaqtning o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgani ma‘lum bo‘lgan. Bu esa hududda turli tarixiy etnik va madaniy jarayonlar sodir bo‘lganidan dalolat beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘istonning ushbu yodgorliklari va arxeologik manzillari sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasining turizm salohiyati juda katta bo‘lib, uni jahon turizm bozoriga zamonaviy marketing vositalari orqali chiqarish imkoni bor. Bu borada ekologik va etnografik turizm muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu turizm yo‘nalishlari nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki uning madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga yoyishda ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mazkur anjuman, ayniqsa, Qoraqalpog‘istonning kelgusi turizm salohiyatini mustahkamlashda, asosiy yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan takliflarni keng tatbiq qilishda omil bo‘lib, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish va yangi turizm xizmatlarini joriy qilishga, hudud aholisi uchun yetarli darajada doimiy va mavsumiy daromadli ish o‘rinlari yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

1 <https://ensiklopediya.uz>

II-SHO'BA

Etnografik turizmni
tashkil etishning
asosiy xususiyatlari

DEVELOPING THROUGH HERITAGE TOURISM

Dr. Hasan Ali Erdoğan

Faculty of TourismNEU, Konya, TURKIYE

A Short History

Heritage Tourism (HT), as a concept, has emerged as a pivotal component in the global tourism industry, reflecting an increasing interest in the preservation and promotion of cultural, historical, and natural heritage. Its development stems from a confluence of factors including globalization, the rise of the experience economy, and a growing recognition of the intrinsic value of preserving cultural identity and historical legacies. HT has its roots in the late 19th and early 20th centuries when affluent travelers, predominantly from Europe, embarked on «grand tours» to explore cultural landmarks and historical sites. However, it wasn't until the latter half of the 20th century that HT began to gain momentum as a distinct tourism niche. The UNESCO World Heritage Convention of 1972 played a crucial role by establishing a framework for the identification, protection, and preservation of cultural and natural heritage sites of outstanding universal value. This international

recognition sparked increased interest in heritage conservation and stimulated tourism to these sites. Furthermore, advancements in transportation, communication, and technology have facilitated easier access to remote destinations, thereby expanding the scope of HT. The proliferation of digital platforms and social media has also amplified awareness and engagement with heritage sites, enabling virtual exploration and fostering a sense of connection among global audiences.

The Significance

HT holds multifaceted significance at both individual and societal levels. Firstly, it serves as a vehicle for cultural exchange and understanding, allowing visitors to immerse themselves in diverse traditions, customs, and lifestyles. Through interactions with local communities and heritage practitioners, tourists gain insights into the historical narratives and socio-cultural dynamics that shape a destination's identity. Moreover, HT contributes to economic development by generating revenue, employment opportunities, and

infrastructure investment in host communities. According to a study by Timothy and Boyd, HT has a multiplier effect, stimulating growth in related sectors such as hospitality, retail, and transportation. Additionally, heritage preservation efforts often entail restoration and conservation projects, which create jobs and stimulate local craftsmanship and heritage-related industries. From a conservation perspective, HT plays a pivotal role in safeguarding endangered cultural and natural assets. By promoting

archaeotourism, prioritize environmental conservation, cultural authenticity, and equitable benefit-sharing, thus mitigating the negative impacts of mass tourism.

Societies develop through heritage tourism

HT accounts for over 43% of all global tourism facilities. Developing HT involves a multifaceted approach that integrates preservation, promotion, and sustainable management of cultural and natural assets to enhance visitor experiences while safeguarding heritage resources. A crucial aspect is

Examples from Çatalhöyük (prehistoric area) and Tyana (ancient Roman city)

sustainable tourism practices and fostering a sense of stewardship among visitors, heritage sites can be preserved for future generations. Sustainable tourism initiatives, such as community-based tourism and ecotourism,

the identification and documentation of significant heritage sites, which requires comprehensive research and stakeholder collaboration (UNESCO, 1972).

Engaging local communities in the

planning and management process is essential for ensuring authenticity and fostering community ownership (Dallen & Boyd, 2011). Interpretation and storytelling play a significant role in HT development, enabling visitors to connect with the historical narratives and cultural significance of a destination (Timothy & Boyd, 2006). Moreover, sustainable tourism practices, such as carrying capacity management and visitor education, are imperative to mitigate negative impacts on heritage sites and surrounding ecosystems (Mowforth & Munt, 2009). By adopting a holistic and participatory approach, HT can contribute to sustainable development while preserving the integrity and authenticity of cultural and natural heritage. The question is «how».

How to turn a heritage site an opportunity for recovery & development

In my opinion, the answer to this question is 5 steps in a hierarchical order:

Scientists do the first job of Creating Story to attract!

As the first step, the development of a heritage area into a tourist destination hinges significantly on the contributions of scientists across various disciplines. Archaeologists play a important role in uncovering and interpreting historical artifacts and sites, providing invaluable insights into the cultural significance of the area (Erdogan, 2020; Smith, 2018). Geologists contribute by assessing the geological formations and landscapes, which not only add to the aesthetic appeal but also aid in understanding the environmental context of the heritage

site (Jones et al., 2020). Environmental scientists evaluate the impact of tourism on the ecosystem, ensuring sustainable practices to preserve the area's natural resources (Gössling & Scott, 2012). Moreover, social scientists analyze visitor behavior and preferences, informing the development of visitor centers, interpretive materials, and immersive experiences tailored to enhance visitor engagement and understanding (McIntosh et al., 2017). Collaboration among scientists fosters a holistic approach to HT development, ensuring the preservation of cultural and natural resources while maximizing the socio-economic benefits for local communities. In short, archaeologists, anthropologists, historians and some other literary personalities come together and collaborate/work over a particular heritage destination.

Central/Local Governments do the second job of developing systems to handle every category in the process.

Central/local governments implement policies and initiatives that preserve cultural heritage while fostering sustainable tourism. At the central level, governments often provide funding, establish regulatory frameworks, and enact laws to protect and promote heritage sites (UNESCO, 2012). These efforts are crucial for safeguarding historical landmarks and traditions while ensuring their accessibility to tourists. Additionally, central governments may collaborate with international organizations like UNESCO to gain recognition for heritage sites, thus attracting global

visitors. On the other hand, local governments are instrumental in implementing conservation projects, infrastructure development, and community engagement initiatives tailored to the specific needs of heritage destinations (Richards & Munsters, 2010). By working closely with local communities and stakeholders, local governments can ensure that tourism development aligns with cultural values, enhances local economies, and fosters pride in heritage (Dredge & Jenkins, 2003). The synergy between central and local governments is essential for the sustainable development of HT destinations, balancing conservation efforts with economic benefits and local empowerment.

Local People do the third job of Maintaining Tourism to activate!

Local people protect the heritage, create activities, produce/sell it, provide service, and connect/convince customers. Thus, the involvement of local communities contributes diverse perspectives and intimate knowledge of the site's history and cultural significance (Moscardo, 2014). Local residents often serve as cultural ambassadors, sharing traditional practices, stories, and folklore that enrich the visitor experience (Richards & Munsters, 2010). Their active participation in heritage preservation efforts, such as maintaining historic buildings or organizing cultural events, fosters a sense of ownership

Examples from Karakalpakstan

Qoraqalpog'iston turizm infratuzilmasi
Туристическая инфраструктура Каракалпакстана
Tourism infrastructure of Karakalpakstan

Area Managers do the fifth job of Sustaining a Living Tourism System!

Communication Specialists do the fourth job of Publicity-Promoting the destination identity to survive!

and pride, enhancing the authenticity of the tourist experience (Battaino et al., 2019). Additionally, local entrepreneurs play a crucial role in creating tourism-related businesses, offering accommodation, guided tours, and locally sourced products, thereby stimulating economic growth and creating employment opportunities within the community (Farsari et al., 2019).

Collaboration between local stakeholders and authorities ensures that tourism development aligns with community needs and values, promoting sustainable practices that safeguard both cultural heritage and the well-being of residents (Hall et al., 2012). Ultimately, the active involvement

of local people is indispensable in shaping a heritage area into a thriving and authentic tourist destination. So, they must be made those who earn the first and the most from the tourism

Examples from Türkiye

Through strategic communication and marketing efforts, these professionals facilitate the promotion of the heritage site, effectively conveying its historical and cultural significance to potential visitors. Research by Morrison and Anderson (2003) underscores the importance of crafting compelling narratives that resonate with target audiences, highlighting the unique attributes and experiences offered by the heritage area, and this shapes the perception and attractiveness of heritage

areas, ultimately contributing to their successful transformation into thriving tourist destinations. Moreover, effective communication strategies, as outlined by Getz (2008), involve leveraging various platforms such as social media, websites, TVs, documentaries, theatres, and promotional materials to reach diverse markets and generate interest and identity in the destination. By fostering engagement and a sense of connection with the heritage site, communication specialists contribute significantly to its sustainable tourism development (Richards, 2001).

Encouraging, fostering, setting through coordinating, collaborating, communicating, theorizing, practicing, and realizing are all a part of sustainable HT to be tackled by area managers. Their responsibilities include overseeing the preservation of cultural and historical assets, managing visitor experiences, and ensuring the sustainable development of tourism activities in these areas. According to Timothy and Boyd (2003), area managers are essential for coordinating efforts to balance the preservation of heritage with the economic benefits of tourism, as well as addressing issues such as visitor impact and community involvement. Additionally, Leask and Fyall (2006) highlight the importance of area managers in implementing strategic plans for HT destinations, which involve collaboration with stakeholders and the integration of conservation practices into tourism management strategies. To be brief, the role of area managers is integral to the effective management

and promotion and thus maintenance of HT, contributing to the preservation of cultural heritage and the enhancement of visitor experiences.

In conclusion, HT has evolved into a dynamic and influential force within the global tourism landscape, driven by a growing appreciation for cultural diversity, historical legacy, and environmental/cultural conservation. Its significance extends beyond economic gains to encompass socio-cultural enrichment, heritage preservation, and sustainable development. As the world continues to grapple with issues of cultural heritage conservation and tourism sustainability, the role of heritage tourism as a catalyst for positive change becomes increasingly vital.

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